

EFFECT OF DIFFERENT IPM MODULES ON SHOOT FLY *Atherigona soccata* (Rondani) DEAD HEARTS, GRAIN AND FODDER YIELD OF KHARIF SORGHUM.Aher S.D.^{*1}, Ilyas., M.D.^{*2}, Ambilwade P.P.^{*3}Timke S. H.^{*4}

1. Department of Agril. Entomology, Vasantao Naik Marathwada Krishi Vidyapeeth, Parbhani-431402, India.

2. Department of Agril. Entomology, Sorghum Research Satation, Vasantao Naik Marathwada Krishi Vidyapeeth, Parbhani-431402, India.

Department of Agril. Entomology, Sorghum Research Satation, Vasantao Naik Marathwada Krishi Vidyapeeth, Parbhani-431402, India.

4. Department of Agril. Entomology, Vasantao Naik Marathwada Krishi Vidyapeeth, Parbhani-431402, India.

sandipaher7878@gmail.com

. (MS Received: 10.01.2023; MS Revised: 11.02.2023; MS Accepted: 12.03.2023)

MS 2987

(RESEARCH PAPER IN ENTOMOLOGY.)

Abstract:

A field trial was scheduled at Sorghum Research Station, VNMKV Parbhani (MS) India. Management of shoot pests of sorghum Randomized Block Design (RBD) with seven treatments and three replications were used. In management of shoot pests different IPM apparatus used against shoot fly dead hearts at 28 DAE Pooled data kharif 2018-19 and 2019-20. Extensively minimum per cent of dead hearts were recorded in the treatment T₄ [Seed treatment with imidacloprid @ 3g ai/kg seed+ *Bacillus thuringiensis* 20 ml/10 lit. of water at 35 DAE] (8.61 %) and all the treatments are statistically at par with each other except untreated control. In perception of grain and fodder, highest 29.08 and 69.39 q/ha yield was recorded in treatment T₅ (FA of Carbofuron 3g @ 20 kg/ha + WA of carbofuron 3g @ 8 kg/ha at 35 DAE).

Key Ward- Bio-efficacy of Insecticides- Sorghum Pest- Sorghum Shoot Fly.

Introduction

Sorghum [*Sorghum bicolor* (L.) Moench] is an important cereal crop in India popularly known as 'Jowar', or 'Great millet'. It is mainly originated in East Central Africa and it was acquainted with India. The benefit of this cereal crop is that it can be cultivated in both Kharif and Rabi season. Sorghum is important feed and food crop in the world and utilized as fodder to feed millions of animals providing milk and meat for human being. Sorghum is nutritious its fodder contains in excess of 50 percent digestible nutrients with 8 percent protein, 2.5 per cent fat and 45 percent nitrogen free concentrate. Maharashtra is foremost sorghum growing states in the country with an area, production, productivity of jowar was 2.23 Million ha, 1.61 Million tonnes and 720 kg ha⁻¹, respectively (Anonymous 2019). Numerous reasons have been attributed for the low grain and fodder yield of sorghum. Among them insect pests ravage is one of the principle factors. Insect pests continue to compete with humans for the sorghum crop and knowledge of both old and new pests has accumulated at a faster rate in recent years as the crop has received increasing attention. About 150 insect species have been recorded on sorghum including in both field as well as store condition. Out of which 31 species are economically important. In Maharashtra about 18 important insect pests have been recorded on sorghum crop. Though a large number of pests have been reported on sorghum crop in Maharashtra very few have economic status. The

No. of plants with dead hearts in a plot

Dead hearts (%) =

Total no. of plants in the plot

x 100.

Result and Discussion

Season 2018-19 all the treatments were found significantly superior for shoot fly dead hearts @ 28 DAE over untreated control. On 28th days after emergence the per cent dead hearts recorded ranged between 9.65 to 47.40. Significantly minimum per cent of dead hearts were recorded in the treatment T₅ [Furrow application of Carbofuran 3% G @ 20 kg/ha + whorl application of carbofuron 3g @ 8 kg/ha at 35 Days after emergence] (9.65%) while rest of the treatments (except T₇ untreated control) found statistically at par with T₄ [Seed treatment with Imidacloprid @ 3g ai/kg seed + *Bacillus thuringiensis* 20 ml/10 Lit. of water at 35 date] (10.03%), T₂ [Seed treatment with imidacloprid @ 3 gm ai/kg seed + Whorl application carbofuron 3g @ 8 kg/ha at 35 Days after emergence] (12.17%), T₃ [Seed treatment with imidacloprid @ 3g ai/kg seed+ spray of Neem seed kernel extract 5% at 35 DAE] (12.25%), T₁ [Seed treatment with imidacloprid @ 3g ai/kg seed] (13.67%) and T₆ [Furrow application of carbofuron 3g @ 20 kg/ha+ NAAS Rating 2022 - 4.51

major being sorghum shoot fly, *Atherigona soccata* Rondani, stem borer, *Chilo partellus* Swinhoe, sorghum shoot bug, *Perigrinu smaidis* Ashmead, earhead bug, *Calocoris angustatus* Lethir, army worm, *Mythimna separate* Walker, midge fly, *Contarinia sorghicola* Coquillette, sorghum aphid, *Melanaphis sacchari* Zehntner, earhead hairy caterpillar, *Euproctis subnotata* Walker and Ear head worm *Helicoverpa armigera* Hubner (Reddy and Davies, 1979).

The shoot fly, *Atherigona soccata* gets attracted from second to seventh leaf period of seedling and placed cigar shaped white eggs singly on the lower surface of the leaves. The maggot of shoot fly after hatching, crawl to the plant whorl and then cut the growing point/tissue and then feed on decaying leaf tissues. As a result central shoot become pale yellow and subsequently dead hearts forms. The tillers may be formed in about two week old seedlings but they may also get damaged. The losses due to shoot fly only were to the tune of 22.11 to 83.94 per cent (Jotwani and Sukhani, 1971; Mote *et. al.*, 1981 and 1982).

Materials and Methods

Observations were recorded for shoot fly, stem borer and ear head worm in each plot and replication on following basis. Shoot fly (*Atherigona soccata*). The dead heart caused by shoot fly was counted at 14th, 21st and 28th days after emergence from total number of plant and per cent dead heart was calculated by using Abbott's (1925) formula:

spray of Novaluron 10 % at 35 Days after emergence] (13.76%). The treatment significantly highest 47.40 per cent of shoot fly dead hearts were recorded in the treatment T₇ untreated control. While highest grain and fodder yield (q/ha) were recorded in treatment T₅ [Furrow application of Carbofuran 3% G @ 20 kg/ha + whorl application of carbofuron 3g @ 8 kg/ha at 35 Days after emergence] 27.81 and 66.33 q/ha, while lowest grain and fodder yield (q/ha) were recorded 10.80 and 34.00 q/ha in Treatment T₇ Untreated control.

Similarly, research trial was scheduled in Season 2019-20 all the treatments were found significantly superior for shoot fly dead hearts @ 28 DAE as compared to untreated control. On 28th days after emergence the per cent dead hearts recorded ranged between 7.19 to 25.52. Significantly minimum per cent of dead hearts were recorded in the treatment T₄ [Seed treatment with imidacloprid @ 3g ai /kg seed+ *Bacillus thuringiensis* 20 ml/10 lit. of water at 35 Days after emergence] (7.19%), while all remaining treatments except T₇ untreated control

found at par with T₅ [Furrow application of Carbofuran 3% G @ 20 kg/ha + whorl application of carbofuron 3g @ 8 kg/ha at 35 Days after emergence] (8.05%), T₂ [Seed treatment with imidacloprid @ 3 g ai/kg seed + Whorl application carbofuron 3g @ 8 kg/ha at 35 Days after emergence] (8.17%), T₃ [Seed treatment with imidacloprid @ 3g ai/kg seed+ spray of Neem seed kernel extract 5% at 35 DAE] (8.52%), T₁ [Seed treatment with imidacloprid @ 3g ai/kg seed] (9.17 %) and T₆ [Furrow application of carbofuron 3g @ 20 kg/ha+ spray of Novaluron 10 % at 35 Days after emergence] (9.54 %). Significantly highest 25.52 per cent of shoot fly dead hearts were recorded in the treatment T₇ untreated control. Highest grain and fodder yield (q/ha) were recorded in treatment T₅ [Furrow application of Carbofuran 3% G @ 20 kg/ha + whorl application of carbofuron 3g @ 8 kg/ha at 35 Days after emergence] 30.34 and 72.44 q/ha, while lowest grain and fodder yield (q/ha) were recorded 8.35 and 34.00 q/ha in Treatment T₇ Untreated control.

Season 2018-19 and 2019-20 pooled data represent that, all treatments were found significantly superior for shoot fly dead hearts @ 28 DAE as compared to untreated control. On 28th days after emergence the per cent dead hearts recorded ranged between 8.61 to 36.46. Significantly minimum per cent of dead hearts were recorded in the treatment T₄ [Seed treatment with imidacloprid @ 3g ai/kg seed + *Bacillus thuringiensis* 20 ml/10 lit. of water at 35 DAE] (8.61 %) while all the treatments were found statistically at par with T₅ [Furrow application of carbofuron 3g @ 20 kg/ha + whorl application of carbofuron 3g @ 8 kg/ha at 35 DAE] (8.85%), T₂ [Seed treatment with imidacloprid @ 3 g ai/kg seed + Whorl application carbofuron 3g @ 8 kg/ha at 35 Days after emergence] (10.17%), T₃ [Seed treatment with imidacloprid @ 3g ai/kg seed+ spray of Neem seed kernel extract 5% at 35 DAE] (10.38%), T₁ [Seed treatment with imidacloprid @ 3g ai/kg seed] (11.42) and T₆ [Furrow application of carbofuron 3g @ 20 kg/ha + spray of Novaluron 10 % at 35 DAE] (11.65). Highest 36.46 per cent of shoot

fly dead hearts were recorded in the treatment T₇ untreated control. Highest grain and fodder yield (q/ha) were recorded in treatment T₅ [Furrow application of Carbofuran 3% G @ 20 kg/ha + whorl application of carbofuron 3g @ 8 kg/ha at 35 Days after emergence] 29.08 and 69.39 q/ha, while lowest grain and fodder yield (q/ha) were recorded 9.58 and 34.00 q/ha in Treatment T₇ Untreated control.

Summery and Conclusion

Significantly minimum per cent of dead hearts was recorded in protected treatment T₄ (ST with Imidacloprid@3gm ai/kg seed + Bt. 20 ml/10 lit. of water at 35 DAE (8.61%) in *Kharif* 2018 and *Kharif* 2019. Highest Grain and fodder yield q/ha recorded in treatment number T₄ (ST with Imidacloprid @ 3 gm ai/kg seed+ Bt. 20 ml/10 lit. of water at 35 DAE) 29.08 and 69.39 q/ha.

References

1. **Anonymous (2019)**. Agriculture statistics at a glance 2019. pp 83-84.
2. **Jotwani, M.G. and Sukhani, T.R. (1971)**. Seed treatment for the control of sorghum shoot fly. *Pesticides*, **5**(4):13-14.
3. **Mote, U.N. and Pokharkar, D.S. (1981)**. Effect of different dates of sowing on the incidence of earhead worm complex on different cultivars. *Sorghum News Lett.*, **24** : 81.
4. **Mote, U.N., Bapat, D.R. and Kadam, J.R. (1982)**. Present status of the improvement pests in Maharashtra and their impact on production. Paper presented to the sorghum workshop held at College of Agriculture, Pune, May 17-19, 1982.
5. **Reddy, K.V.S. and Davies, J.G. (1979)**. Pests of sorghum and pearl millet and their parasites and predators recorded at ICRISAT centre up to August, 1977, *Cereal Entomology Progress Report-2*, Patancheru, India. pp 58-61.

Table. 1 Bio efficacy of different IPM components against major insect pests of sorghum and their effect on grain and fodder yield in Kharif 2018.

Treatment No	Treatment Details	% SFDH at 28DAE	Grainyield (q/ha)	Fodder yield(q/ha)
1	ST with Imidacloprid @3gm ai/kg seed	13.67 (21.61)	16.51	41.61
2	ST with Imidacloprid@3g ai/kg seed + WA carbofuron 3g @ 8 kg/ha at 35 DAE	12.17 (20.34)	28.69	68.37
3	ST with Imidacloprid @3gm ai/kg seed +Spray of NSKE 5% at 35 DAE	12.25 (20.40)	20.06	56.48
4	ST with Imidacloprid @ 3gm ai/kg seed + Bt.20 ml/10 lit. of water at 35DAE	10.03 (18.35)	22.05	62.56
5	FA of Carbofuron 3g@20 kg/ha +WA of carbofuron3g@ 8 kg/ha at 35 DAE	9.65 (17.94)	27.81	66.33
6	FA of Carbofuron 3g@ 20 kg/ha + Spray of Novaluron10%at 35 DAE	13.76 (21.62)	23.57	65.95
7	UntreatedControl	47.40 (43.48)	10.80	34.00
	SE	2.39	2.69	6.13
	CD	5.26	5.92	13.50
	CV	12.5	15.42	13.29

Figures in parentheses are angular transformed value, SFDH=Shoot fly Dead Hearts, ST= Seed Treatment, FA= Farrow Applications, WA=Whorl application, DAE= Day after Emergence.

Table 2.Bio efficacy of different IPM components against major insect pests of sorghum and their effect on grain and fodder yield in Kharif 2019.

Treatment No	Treatment Details	%SFDH at 28 DAE	Grainyield (q/ha)	Fodder yield (q/ha)
1	ST with Imidacloprid @3g ai./kg seed	9.17 (17.52)	15.60	40.27
2	STwithImidacloprid@3 g ai/kg seed + WA carbofuron 3g@ 8 kg/ha at 35 DAE.	8.17 (16.4)	30.89	73.75
3	ST with Imidacloprid@3 g ai/kg seed + Spray of NSKE 5 % at 35 DAE	8.52 (16.62)	25.43	57.47
4	ST with Imidacloprid @3 g ai/kg seed+ Bt.20 ml/ 10lit. of water at 35 DAE	7.19 (15.09)	26.16	62.38
5	FA of Carbofuron 3g@20 kg/ha + WA of carbofuron3g@ 8 kg/ha at 35 DAE	8.05 (16.02)	30.34	72.44
6	FA of Carbofuron 3g@ 20 kg/ha + Spray of Novaluron 10%at 35 DAE	9.54 (17.83)	24.77	65.95
7	UntreatedControl	25.52 (30.32)	8.35	34.00
	SE	2.29	2.83	6.50
	CD	5.04	6.23	14.30
	CV	15.13	15.01	13.70

Figures in parentheses are angular transformed value, SFDH=Shoot fly Dead Hearts, ST= Seed Treatment, FA= Farrow Applications, WA=Whorl application, DAE= Day after Emergence.

Table 3. Bio efficacy of different IPM components against major insect pests of sorghum and their effect on grain and fodder yield in *Kharif* 2018, 2019 and pooled data.

Treatment No	Treatment Details	%SFDH at 28DAE	Grain yield (q/ha)	Fodder yield (q/ha)
1	ST with Imidacloprid @3g ai/kg seed	11.42 (19.71)	16.05	40.94
2	ST with Imidacloprid@3gai/kg seed +WA carbofuron 3g@ 8 kg/ha at 35 DAE	10.17 (18.48)	29.79	71.06
3	ST with Imidacloprid @3 g ai/kg seed + Spray of NSKE 5% at 35 DAE	10.38 (18.76)	22.75	56.98
4	STwith Imidacloprid @3g ai/kg seed+ Bt.20ml /10 lit. of water at 35 DAE	8.61 (16.91)	24.11	62.47
5	FA of Carbofuron 3g@20 kg/ha+WA of carbofuron 3g@ 8 kg/ha at 35 DAE	8.85 (17.04)	29.08	69.39
6	FA of Carbofuron 3g @ 20 kg/ha + Spray of Novaluron10% at 35 DAE.	11.65 (19.86)	24.17	65.96
7	Untreated Control	36.46 (37.12)	9.58	34.00
	SE	1.80	2.23	5.70
	CD	3.98	4.90	12.55
	CV	10.48	12.27	12.18

Figures in parentheses are angular transformed value, SFDH=Shoot fly Dead Hearts, ST= Seed Treatment, FA= Farrow Applications, WA=Whorl application, DAE= Day after Emergence.